

Search for New Antiviral Agents-Part I. Synthesis of 2-phenyl-3-(alkyl-benzimidazolyl) quinazolin-4-ones

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Ten new benzimidazolyl-quinazolone derivatives have been synthesised with a view to test their antiviral activity.

QUINAZOLONE derivatives exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties, such as central nervous system depressant¹⁻³, anticonvulsant⁴⁻⁵, anticarcinogenic⁶, muscle relaxant^{6,7} and anti-parkinsonism⁸. Although the efficacy of this class of compounds in combating the diseases caused by viruses has not yet been established, it seems worthwhile that with structural modifications these derivatives might prove useful in this condition. Further, benzimidazole derivatives exhibit pronounced antiviral activity⁹⁻¹³ and are the potent inhibitor of the growth of influenza virus. In the present studies, both quinazolone and benzimidazole moieties have been united with the expectation of getting compounds with enhanced antiviral activity as well as potency.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route :

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulphuric acid melting point bath and are uncorrected.

2-Amino methyl/ethyl benzimidazole(I) : A mixture of the equimolar amounts of *o*-phenylenediamine and glycine/dl- α -alanine was heated for 2½ hours under reflux in the presence of conc. HCl. Subsequently, reaction mixture was concentrated and the desired product separated out on cooling. Compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3, 1(4H)-benzoxazine 4-one(II) : The procedure described by Sammour et al¹⁴ was

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Mole. For.	Analysis Nitrogen	
				Cal.	Found
1.	H	248°	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃	28.76%	28.93%
2.	CH ₃	195°	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃	26.09%	25.86%

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Mole. For.	Analysis Nitrogen	
				Cal.	Found
1.	H	above 300°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	15.90%	16.15%
2.	CH ₃	above 300°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	15.32%	15.68%

Note : The solvent used for recrystallization was ethanol. The yield ranged from 50-60%.

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis Nitrogen	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	H	- α -(β -naphthyl)	219°(d)	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	11.02%	10.81%
2.	H	-phthalimido	115°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	13.69%	14.01%
3.	H	-benzamido	186-87°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	14.43%	14.76%
4.	H	- α -(<i>o</i> -cresolyl)	142°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	11.86%	12.08%
5.	H	-nicotinamido	above 300°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	14.83%	14.66%
6.	CH ₃	- α '(β -naphthyl)	220°(d)	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.72%	10.92%
7.	CH ₃	-phthalimido	134-35°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	13.33%	12.92%
8.	CH ₃	-benzamido	199-200°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	14.03%	14.42%
9.	CH ₃	- α -(<i>o</i> -cresolyl)	134-35°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	11.52%	11.26%
10.	CH ₃	-nicotinamido	above 300°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	14.40%	14.13%

Note: The solvent used for recrystallisation was ethanol. The yield ranged from 50-60%. The i.r. spectra for carbonyl in the ring (1620 cm⁻¹) and free phenolic hydroxyl (3300 cm⁻¹) further support the validity of the above compounds.

followed. Thus, anthranilic acid (0.01 mole) was dissolved in pyridine (30 ml). The solution was cooled and benzoyl chloride (0.01 mole) was added dropwise with constant shaking. After the addition was complete, the mixture was further stirred for half an hour at room temperature. It was then treated with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove any unreacted acid. When the effervescence ceased, it was filtered and washed repeatedly with water in order to remove adhered pyridine. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. = 122°.

2-Phenyl-3-alkyl-[2'-benzimidazolyl] 3,1(4H)quinazolin-4-one(III): A mixture of 2-phenyl, 3,1(4H)-benzoxazin 4-one (0.01 mole) and 2-amino methyl/ethyl-benzimidazole (0.01 mole) in 30 ml of dry pyridine was refluxed for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was poured in the ice cooled water containing dil. HCl. The solid product that separated out, was washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from dil. ethanol. The various compounds thus synthesised are recorded in Table 2.

2-Phenyl-3-alkyl-[1'-methyl-arylsubstituted 2'-benzimidazolyl] 3,1(4H)-quinazolin-4-one(IV): A mixture of reactive hydrogen compound (0.005 mole), the above quinazolinone (0.005 mole), formaldehyde solution (10 ml.) and a few drops of conc. HCl. was heated under reflux for 3 hours. It was cooled. A solid product separated out, which was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol. The compounds thus synthesized are recorded in Table 3.

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